

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Aber**FIRST NAME:** Peace**PROGRAM CODE:** DEPI**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:**1**INSTRUCTOR:** Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 15%

The author used the following software: MSWord V2409 on Windows 10 pro

List your 5-7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Essay writing (EUCLID 2024, 6–14)
2. Punctuations (EUCLID 2024, 15–23)
3. American versus British English (EUCLID 2024, 24–32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 33–39)
5. Style guide (EUCLID 2024, 40–42)
6. Chicago style (EUCLID 2024, 43–57)
7. Latin abbreviations (EUCLID 2024, 58–64)

FUNDAMENTALS OF PAPER WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

In my journey as a Doctorate student at EUCLID, this is my first interaction with study material for the first period of the first course. It has taken me a while to acquaint myself with EUCLID University's operations. I decided to give myself ample time to familiarize myself with expectations from me as a student, where to get help along the way, and to see which courses I will be studying as I go along. I understand that these aspects are important and have given me a good foundation for my journey at the University.

Reading about paper writing has been interesting and eye-opening. It has made me understand that consistency is important for professional writing. I have been enlightened in many ways, as seen in the focus areas below.

2) ESSAY WRITING

Essay writing is an important communication form used in various settings. One important form of essay writing for students at EUCLID is the academic essay, also known as scholarly writing (EUCLID 2024, 7). As a Doctorate student at EUCLID, I have noted that all my coursework must be written properly before submission. Furthermore, to produce quality essays, one must plan essay writing beforehand. Moreover, different parts of the essay should be well thought out before embarking on the writing process. I have noted that academic writers are encouraged to start by writing the essay's body first and then write the introduction and conclusion (EUCLID 2024, 11). During the writing process, I need to set aside my work before editing to look at my work with a fresh eye after about two days of writing.

I have noted that it is also important to reference one's work during the writing process. Whereas many referencing styles can be used, writers need to understand the referencing style acceptable by the institution receiving the written work. I have therefore paid attention to the referencing style acceptable by EUCLID. EUCLID recommends using the Turabian referencing style, although it may accept any other referencing style for different categories of students (EUCLID 2024, 11).

Submitting the completed work is also important during essay writing. Writers must submit work in a format that is guided by the course. Determining how the lecturer/ tutor would like assignments presented is crucial, and ensuring you comply with the requirements is equally crucial (EUCLID 2024, 12). I have seen that students at EUCLID should submit their assignments by emailing the course instructor and attaching the response papers to the email (EUCLID 2024, 12).

3) PUNCTUATIONS

Punctuation is an integral part of writing. I have noted that it is important to know all the punctuation and their correct usage. These include, but are not limited to, apostrophes, bullet points, commas, and quotation marks. In as much as one can use any of the appropriate punctuation in sentences, it is advisable to use as few punctuations in sentences as possible (EUCLID 2024, 16).

I have noted the use of the apostrophe in writing. The apostrophe is an important punctuation that is used to indicate possession. It is generally used after singular nouns, plural nouns that do not end in s, and indefinite pronouns. Although this is a common rule, I have seen that names of places don't necessarily follow this rule. It is, therefore, important to check from known sources whether apostrophes apply to names of specific places (EUCLID 2024, 16).

As I went through the course pack, I noted that sentences generally end with full stops or question marks. It is interesting to note that this does not necessarily apply to writing when using bullet points. While using bullet points, full sentences end with full

colons, while the last sentence ends with a full stop. I have also paid attention to the fact that words that do not form full sentences within bullet points do not contain any punctuation at all (EUCLID 2024, 18).

4) AMERICAN VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH

During this course, I have learned of marked differences between American and British English usage. In my previous work, I have used both American and British English without paying attention to the differences between the two. I have, therefore, had many instances where I have used both within the same document. Although there are marked differences between the two variants of English, they are more similar than different (EUCLID 2024, 25).

The important differences that I have paid attention to include differences in punctuation, use of pluralized adjectives, pronunciation, spelling, and the use of punctuation in emails. I have noted that while writing emails, US English requires one to place a full colon after the addressee, while UK English requires a comma after the same (EUCLID 2024, 32). I had never really paid attention to this in my previous writing. Further, I understood that UK English requires the use of inverted commas for quotations, while US English requires the use of double quotation marks while making quotations (EUCLID 2024, 31).

Overall, I have been guided that it is important to stick to one variant of English during this course. I will be using US English during my course assignments based on EUCLID guidance.

5) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is defined as the failure to give credit to an author when using their work (EUCLID 2024, 34). In my interaction with the study material, I have seen that plagiarism takes different forms and can apply to students and non-students. One common example among students is having someone else do an assignment and hand it in as their own (EUCLID 2024, 34).

In addition to being wrong and unethical, I have noted that plagiarism is a serious academic offense. It can, therefore, lead to consequences such as scoring lower grades or even rejecting submitted work. To avoid plagiarism, I have learned that quoting or citing other people's work is important. Quotations should be placed in quotation marks if they are short enough. Long quotations, on the other hand, should be inserted into the document using the quote style in Word. Further still, it is important to have in-text citations within documents to acknowledge other people's work (EUCLID 2024, 35). I have learned that sticking to one citation style within one document is important. In this document, I have used the Turabian style to cite work from other sources.

6) STYLE GUIDE

Style guides are general rules that guide writers in presenting certain elements of written work (EUCLID 2024, 41). I have realized that it is essential to ensure consistency in writing, especially when there are many contributing authors to a document. Writing styles encompass various aspects, including font usage, spelling, abbreviations, symbols, manuscript layouts, etc.

At EUCLID, students are encouraged to use the Turabian style of writing. I believe this aims to ensure consistency in writing among the various students. There are generally many style guides; it is recommended to download a guiding document from the internet for a style they wish to use (EUCLID 2024, 42). This is the easiest way to stick to a preferred writing style consistently.

7) CHICAGO STYLE

The Chicago style of writing is one of the many styles of writing that can be used. It has specifications for abbreviations, capitalization, compound words, numbers, and quotations (EUCLID 2024, 47–50). I have noted that scholarly abbreviations, such as, etc., can only be used within parentheses. This is something that I have not been using in my past writings but will adapt.

The Chicago style also emphasizes using hyphens in compound nouns (EUCLID 2024, 46). I understand that compound nouns vary in format, with some requiring hyphens while others do not. I have acknowledged that the best way to know the correct usage of hyphens with the Chicago style is to cross-check with the dictionary always.

There are specific formatting requirements for the Chicago style of writing. A particular example that I have not paid attention to in the past is justification. In most previous writing, the computer automatically justified my work without paying attention to any implications. This document has made me see the need to manually check all the hyphenations in the document when automatic justification is done (EUCLID 2024, 50). This will ensure the correctness of the words with hyphenation within the document.

8) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS

Latin abbreviations are common expressions that are generally used in writing. Such expressions include, etc., N.B, P.M, A.M, and so on. In the past, I have used these abbreviations without necessarily knowing their full format or their English equivalent. I have noted that their usage can be very confusing to different audiences (EUCLID 2024, 59). I see that it is important to use the English equivalent of the Latin abbreviations for business and technical audiences. An example is to use and so on instead of etc. I have therefore tasked myself to continue reading about Latin abbreviations and their English equivalent.

I note that Latin abbreviations are generally appropriate in footnotes and informal writings (EUCLID 2024, 59). In my academic writing at EUCLID, I will mostly keep the Latin abbreviations to footnotes and any informal writing I may have to do. I will also continue to explore and use the English equivalent of Latin words within my documents. This, I believe, will minimize confusion for the audience that will be reading my work.

9) **CONCLUSION**

In conclusion, this has been an interesting start to my DEPI program at EUCLID. I have seen the need to grasp important aspects of paper writing. In the past, I have not paid attention to important aspects of paper writing, such as the need to stick to one variant of English, select a writing style, and create enough time for essay writing. With the knowledge obtained from here, I feel I have the knowledge to excel in my coursework submissions and communication with the business and professional communities.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C. Euclid University Press.

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